

EVALUATING RESEARCH COLLABORATION IN X INSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

Many studies have examined research collaboration related to research productivity and scientific publications. The tendency is that the higher the collaboration level, the higher the productivity. However, these studies do not always explain how the existing collaborations are formed. Even though lecturers in Indonesia have three responsibilities (Tridarma), which include education, research, and community service, these studies are also limited to the research aspect. The other two aspects are considered closely related because community service is considered as a downstream of research. Although qualitative studies can help explain the formation of research collaborations and community service, research on collaborations tends to use bibliometrics or social network analysis. This study seeks to explain the mapping and the formation of research collaborations at the X Institution, from 2020 to 2021, using bibliometric analysis combined with in-depth interviews with various stakeholders. Those years have been the initial period of using Research and Service Information Systems at the faculty level, so the availability of the data helps to describe the collaboration of research and community service at the X Institution. This mapping can be the basis for research and community service policies at the the X Institution.

KEYWORDS

Research collaboration, co-authorship, bibliometrics

INTRODUCTION

Many studies confirm a relationship between research collaboration and researcher productivity (Abramo et al., 2009, 2017; Lee & Bozeman, 2005). Existing research shows that the higher the level of collaboration, the higher the productivity of research publications (Abramo et al., 2009). Researchers have more publication opportunities if they collaborate with other researchers. They can also build relationships to develop their career. Research collaboration also enables the exchange of trans-disciplinary ideas, skills development, funding opportunities, and increased research capacity (Lee & Bozeman, 2005). For institutions, research collaboration increases opportunities for collaboration and plays a role in the global world. Research collaboration between countries allows knowledge transfer (Freshwater et al., 2006; Mark, 2007).

Collaborative research studies tend to be based on network analysis which can utilize bibliometric studies or social network analysis (Lievrouw, 1989; Subramanyam, 1983). This method tends to be criticized because it does not answer the reasons for the formation of the network (Lievrouw, 1989). These studies only describe the relationship map formed by the relationship between actors. Lievrouw has suggested that collaborative research use ethnographic methods, case studies, or phenomenology (Lievrouw, 1989). The qualitative

methods are expected to explain the reasons for the network formation. However, the qualitative method does not allow for the use of extensive data like the studies using the bibliometric method. On the other hand, bibliometrics or social network analysis cannot be abandoned because this method helps map the network of researchers formed by their social relationships. Lievrouw (1989) suggests that qualitative studies can be developed as a follow-up study to explain the reasons for the formation of existing networks.

It is not possible to apply ethnography, case studies, and phenomenology to a broad object in collaborative research as is commonly done with bibliometrics (Lievrouw, 1989). On the other hand, bibliometrics is still needed to reveal the collaborative network map. These two factors cause the scope of collaborative research studies combined with qualitative research to be smaller and more specific. The limited scope allows deeper exploration of the factors and causes forming the relationship between researchers. For example, Kastrin et al. (2018) find that senior researchers play a more important role in promoting a research subject. In addition, senior researchers tend to have more opportunities than junior researchers (Lu et al., 2021). This has implications for the scientific productivity of researchers; in other words, senior researchers usually have more publications than junior researchers. In general, the scientific productivity, influence, number of collaborators, and other indicators of scientific research performance of senior researchers are better than junior researchers (Lu et al., 2021). Several other studies have shown that collaboration is a means of mentoring between senior and junior researchers (Lu et al., 2021). Collaboration also becomes a means of knowledge transfer that allows junior researchers to increase their capacity (Franco & Pinho, 2019; Giuri et al., 2019; Ye et al., 2020).

Research on this limited scope helps us understand the collaboration pattern between researchers within an institution. Elisabeth et al. (2019) have found that the most popular actors influence research themes and bridge the relationship between actors at the Faculty of Computer Science, Universitas Indonesia. Rahmaida, Saefuddin, and Sartono (2019) conducted co-authorship research on the publications of the Indonesian Institute of Sciences (*Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia*). They revealed a co-authoring pattern formed from a series of publications and that future collaboration patterns could be predicted. Arfina and Khotimah (2018) studied the co-authorship of 3701 publications of Institut Pertanian Bogor indexed by Scopus up to 2017; they found that co-authorship was effective in increasing the number of publications.

Based on the explanation above, we used research collaboration and community service data at the X Institution, as a research source. We chose this topic because of the evaluative opportunities for 2020-2021 research and community service data. During that period, the proposal and reporting of faculty research used an information system that archiving occurred properly. This evaluative process was also possible because the research and community service schemes in those years had similarities, making it possible to review the collaborative research. In addition, there is also an opportunity for us, as part of an institution, to conduct interviews and observations of researchers and policymakers. This is relevant to Lievrouw's suggestion to explore further the reasons for the formation of the researcher network.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Co-Authorship Analysis

Bibliometric analysis is a method used to perform evaluations of scientific output and impact (Sulistyo-Basuki, 2016). This method emerged to understand science development quantitatively based on specific characteristics. Statistical calculations then describe a pattern that can be observed for a decision. This pattern can be seen from reading keywords, abstracts, citations, authorship, acknowledgments, or other information available in scientific publications. This pattern provides an understanding of the evolution of knowledge in the object under study (Gingras, 2016; Sulistyo-Basuki, 2016).

Authorship analysis is a sub-method in bibliometrics (Gingras, 2016; Sulistyo-Basuki, 2016). The analysis measures and maps the authors of research papers. Authorship measurement is related to the publication productivity of an author, seen from the number of articles or books the author published. On the other hand, authorship measurement can be reviewed based on author affiliation. This helps to measure the collective productivity of the institution. This kind of measurement can then be the basis for ranking institutions based on publication productivity.

Authorship analysis also deals with mapping the collaboration of authors (Kumar, 2015). It refers to an attempt to explain the relationship between authors of a particular subject. Bibliometrics measures writing patterns (Srivastava et al., 2021). Fatmawati (2012) identified the types of authors in research articles. There are terms known as co-authors and sub-authors. The simple concept of the flow of knowledge occurs from the knowledge owner (researcher) to the knowledge seeker (reader) (Natakusumah, 2016). Authorship is intended for researchers who have contributed to research results (Nelisa, 2012). The author not only contributes to the paper but is also responsible for the entire content of the published work (Natakusumah, 2014).

The results of collaborative research have increased in quantity (Barik & Jena, 2018; Prieto-Gutiérrez & Segado-Boj, 2019). Not only as a means to share competencies and resources, but collaboration is also considered able to build interaction in creating new knowledge (Das, 2013). In addition, studies on specific research topics will also significantly develop if researchers collaborate (Tupan et al., 2018).

Through collaborative studies, the research communication process can be measured and analyzed (Junandi, 2015). Collaborative research can occur at the individual, institutional, or country levels. Collaborative research can be divided into three categories: (1) internal collaboration within the same institution; (2) domestic collaboration by different fellow researchers or institutions within one country; and (3) international collaboration between countries (Maryono & Surajiman, 2017). Collaborative research occurs not only in academic settings—for broader knowledge dissemination, collaborative research also occurs between institutions with different backgrounds. “Triple Helix” is a term for collaborative research between the government, research institutions, and industry (Tupan et al., 2018). Analysis of collaborative research will be easier to trace by presenting data visualization or mapping (Van Eck & Waltman, 2018)

Collaborative Research

Collaborative research shows a mutually dependent and beneficial interaction between

researchers (Katz & Martin, 1997). The dependence is functional, meaning that this relationship is based on the roles and contributions each researcher has in the collaboration; in other words, it is symbiotic mutualism. Every researcher involved in the collaboration gets certain benefits. Material benefits relate to financial benefits obtained from research grants or awards. Immaterial benefits are diverse because researchers can gain new knowledge, relationships, career advancement, or access to broader funding.

Collaborative research tends to be open, allowing various relationships to develop into collaboration. Collaboration can occur at an equal or hierarchical level between researchers, institutions, and countries with the same research interest (Subramanyam, 1983). On the other hand, the unequal hierarchical relationship between lecturers and students, senior-junior researchers, and institutions make collaborative research possible. There are various kinds of collaboration, such as intradisciplinary (research teams within the same department), interdisciplinary (research teams from different departments but of the same background), multidisciplinary (research teams from different backgrounds), or transdisciplinary (involvement of people from outside the departments). Everyone aspires to common demands such as making operational plans, communicating between different research groups, sharing credit and money, holding frequent meetings, and encouraging open communication (Bansal et al., 2019).

Bansal et al. (2019) describe several elements of collaborative research. (1) Collaboration builds open communication channels where participants must be encouraged to take opportunities for older system updates. (2) Collaboration involves all partners and others; they have to provide feedback and engage in self-reflection. (3) Collaboration must identify stakeholders who can serve as a feedback loop to help understand cause and effect. (4) Collaboration also defines clarity of roles and responsibilities. (5) Collaboration builds a professional environment and respects the culture of different organizations.

Bukvova (2010) mentions three things to reveal in studies on collaborative research: (1) factors that influence collaborative research, (2) the development of models and frameworks, and (3) the development of a collaborative typology.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research data came from the information on collaborative research and community services of the X Institution in 2020-2021, which cumulatively consisted of 154 researchers. The researchers formed 14 interconnected clusters and produced 188 titles. The data was obtained through the Research and Community Service Agency X Institution. The data were in the form of a list of team members' names. The relationship between the team leader and team members, which was assumed to be an authorship collaboration, was then analyzed using the co-authorship analysis. Based on the research method, the stages of this research are as follows.

We input authorship collaboration data through the Zotero application. In contrast to other citation applications, Zotero provides a full name feature, so the output format is first name and last name. Folders were grouped by year and research schemes, which were stored in RIS (Research Information System) format. Data were visualized using VosViewer with Fractional Counting. This calculation method allows the determination of more specific clusters in the

network map. We created a thesaurus with an acronym format to prevent overlapping names. Network maps were displayed using Network Visualization.

The VosViewer clustering method employed the Association Strength. We also used three Layout Methods. The *first* is the network per scheme, consisting of *Hibah A, Hibah B, Hibah C, Hibah D, Hibah E, Hibah F, Hibah G, Hibah H dan Hibah I* using No Normalization. The network map tended to form a circle. However, the layout method could provide a distributed view suitable when the network had more separate clusters. The *second* is the network of *Hibah DPKM, Penelitian, dan Pengabdian 2020 dan 2021* using the Association Strength layout method. This method has a weakness in displaying a distributed network. However, this method can identify the network clumps formed.

The *third* is the 2020-2021 cumulative network using the LinLog/Modularity layout method. This method displays cluster distribution, but separate clusters are automatically located in the center of the network, causing separate clusters to appear overlapping. Thus, this method is unsuitable if the network has many labels and wants to identify separate clusters. On the other hand, the 2020-2021 cumulative network is suitable for applying the layout method because it does not have a separate cluster. As a result, the network appears to spread out without changing the clumps formed. In addition, this method also clarifies the label of the author who acts as a liaison between network clusters. The label size displayed in the network map depends on the number of documents. The wider the circle of the author label, the higher the number of documents. Hyphens or links show the relationship between authors. The thicker the lines or links appear, the more often these authors collaborate.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution based on Collaboration per Scheme in 2020 and 2021

Figure 1. Distribution of Total Titles per Scheme

Figure 1 displays 9 schemes that form 4 patterns based on the number of titles from 2020 to 2021 and the combination of the two years. These patterns confirm 4 schemes with a stable frequency: *Hibah E*, *Hibah D*, *Hibah I*, and *Hibah DPKM*. In addition, 3 schemes (*Hibah A*, *Hibah C*, and *Hibah B*) experienced an increase in frequency. An interesting finding is that *Hibah A* has doubled in number from 4 titles in 2020 to 8 titles in 2021. Then, 1 scheme experienced a decrease in frequency, namely *Hibah F*, *Hibah G*, but the decrease was only for 1 title from the total in 2020. Finally, 1 scheme only occurred in 2020, namely *Hibah H* (9 titles). Cumulatively, *Hibah DPKM* became the highest collaboration scheme with 62 titles.

The Collaborative network of *Hibah A*

Figure 2. *Hibah A* 2020-2021

The collaborative research network under the scheme *Hibah A* was formed by 25 authors who produced 12 titles. Figure 2 shows that the authors form 3 patterns with 9 separate clusters. The first and most dominating pattern shows that the collaboration of authors only occurred once a year (Cluster 5 in 2020 and Cluster 2, 3, 4, 6, and 9 in 2021). The number of clusters in 2021 was also related to a doubling in the number of titles (from 4 titles to 8 titles) compared to 2020. The second pattern was the collaboration of the same two authors in 2020 and 2021 (Cluster 8).

In the third pattern, 2 of the 3 researchers collaborated again in 2021 (Cluster 1 and 7). Cluster 1 collaborated on the same topic and research object but with different perspectives. The research used the perspective of self-government in 2020, while the 2021 research used the perspective of collaborative governance. On the other hand, Cluster 7 and 8 researched different topics between 2020 and 2021.

These patterns confirmed that collaborative research on the *Hibah A* scheme tended to be done with different researchers so that they formed separate clusters. However, some researchers conducted research in a row for two years. This successive research could take place because

it discussed a different topic or the continuation of the topic in the previous year.

The Collaborative network of *Hibah B*

Figure 3. *Hibah B* 2020-2021

Hibah B consisted of 36 researchers producing 23 titles. The researchers formed 12 clusters, two of which were connected. Figure 3 shows that the connected clusters are Cluster 1 and 2. In the beginning, the researchers in Cluster 1 (igep, apg, and rew) collaborated in 2020. Then, each of them collaborated with other researchers in 2021. The collaborative network formed Cluster 1. The researchers of Cluster 1 (apg and ord) and Cluster 2 (swt) studied Disaster Governance in 2021. The collaborative research connected Cluster 1 and Cluster 2. In addition, the researcher of Cluster 2 (swt) collaborated twice with different researchers in 2020. Swt collaborated again two times in 2021. Those patterns formed Cluster 2 and identified that collaborative research in 2021 formed a connection between clusters.

The 10 separate clusters formed 3 patterns. First, collaboration only occurred once a year, namely in Cluster 3, 5, and 8 (in 2020) and Cluster 4, 7, and 9 (in 2021). Second, collaboration occurred with the same researchers from 2020 to 2021 (Cluster 6, 10, and 12). Third, collaboration with the same researcher occurred twice in 2020 and once in 2021. The collaboration discussed different topics.

These patterns identified that the collaboration of researchers in the same or different years

could expand the collaboration cluster, as in Cluster 1 and 2. On the other hand, separate clusters occurred due to two factors. First, it occurred because the collaboration of the researchers only took place once every two years. Second, collaboration occurred with the same researchers during 2020-2021.

The Collaborative network of *Hibah C*

Figure 4. *Hibah C* 2020-2021

Hibah C consisted of 22 researchers producing 13 titles. Figure 4 shows that the researchers formed 3 patterns with 8 separate clusters. First, the researchers only collaborated in 2020 (Cluster 8) or 2021 (Cluster 3 and 7). Second, the same researchers collaborated from 2020 to 2021. Researchers in Cluster 2, 4, and 6 collaborated on topics of different titles. Meanwhile, researchers in Cluster 5 collaborated on the same topic regarding corruption. Thus, these researchers both produced 2 titles through *Hibah C*. Third, two researchers re-collaborated with different researchers between 2020-2021. Thus, the network of researchers in Cluster 1 was wider than in other clusters.

The patterns confirmed that 4 collaboration clusters of the same researcher resulted in 8 titles. The collaboration with different researchers between years resulted in 3 titles. The collaboration between 3 researchers with one different researcher for 2 years resulted in 2 titles. Thus, most

consecutive collaborations of the same researcher dominated *Hibah C* in two years.

The Collaborative network of *Hibah D*

Figure 5. *Hibah D* 2020-2021

Hibah D consisted of 48 researchers producing 20 titles. Figure 5 shows that the researchers formed 11 clusters, 3 of which were connected. Cluster 4 was formed in 2020, where sw and ni became the connecting authors. In the same year, the collaboration formed Cluster 6. On the other hand, the collaboration where mfr acted as a liaison occurred in 2020. Then, the collaboration between mfr, mam, and r occurred again with different topics in 2021. In addition, twa collaborated with other researchers (hnu and ryd) in 2021. This pattern caused Cluster 1 to become the widest network. Then Cluster 1, 4, and 5, a collaborative network of lecturers within the field of Departemen Y, were connected. This connection occurred when researchers in Cluster 1 (hnu-associate professor), Cluster 4 (k-associate professor), and Cluster 6 (arh-junior lecturer) conducted collaborative research on business resilience in 2021.

The separate clusters form 4 patterns. First, collaboration only occurred once a year, namely Cluster 5 and 10 (in 2020) and 7, 9, and 11 (in 2021). Second, collaboration occurred between the same researchers but with different topics between years (Cluster 8). Third, collaboration occurred between the same researchers on different topics and years. This pattern occurred in

Cluster 3 when ra collaborated with aw and fa (in 2020) and s, apg, and atw (in 2021). Fourth, collaboration occurred between researchers with the same and different topics and years. Initially, the collaboration took place between mgwe, smr, zh, and srh on Entrepreneurial Knowledge Market Orientation in 2020. Then mgwe, smr, and zh again collaborated with gen on Multi-Channel Marketing and Market Logistics in 2021. Although different, the two collaborations have the same target, namely East Java Small and Medium Enterprises. In the same year, gen also collaborated with ey and ad. This pattern forms Cluster 2.

To sum up, collaboration with several similarities and differences between research members in the same or different years resulted in 12 titles. Thus, repeated collaborations with different researchers dominated the research of *Hibah D* for two years. This also caused the relationship between the 3 clusters.

The Collaborative network of *Hibah E*

Figure 6. *Hibah E* 2020-2021

Hibah E consisted of 33 researchers producing 10 titles. Figure 6 shows the researchers forming 8 clusters, 2 of which are connected. The 8 clusters formed 4 patterns. First, *Hibah E* only occurred in 2020 (Cluster 3, 4, and 7). Second, *Hibah E* occurred in 2021 (Cluster 2 and 8). Third, *Hibah E* occurred with different topics and researchers for two years, but there was one same researcher, with am as a liaison, causing Cluster 1 to become the widest network.

Fourth, two different clusters were connected. Cluster 5 was a collaboration in 2020. Then the researchers (crd, ss, nfn, and bsy-e) collaborated with one of the researchers in Cluster 6 (sw) on the Board of Commissioner in 2021. In the same year, sw collaborated with other researchers of Cluster 6 (kpk, nsa, and zbi-e). *Hibah E* is different from other research schemes because it involves external researchers (label “-e”). Based on this description, the collaboration between different researchers for two years had the same frequency as repeated collaborations between years, with differences in some research members, and they all produced 5 titles.

The Collaborative network of *Hibah F*

Figure 7. *Hibah F*, 2020-2021

Hibah F consisted of 48 researchers producing 19 titles. Figure 7 shows that the researchers formed 9 clusters, 4 of which were connected to form two separate clusters. The first cluster was formed from the connection of Cluster 1 and 2. This cluster was dominated by researchers whose focus was on Departemen Y. This connection occurred when researchers in Cluster 2 (wp, mi, and bys) conducted research with researchers in Cluster 1 (anlif) in 2020.

The second cluster is the connection of Cluster 3 and 4. The cluster was dominated by researchers whose focus was on Departement Z. This connection occurred when researchers in Cluster 3 (am) conducted research with researchers in Cluster 4 (taf and ala) in 2021. On the

other hand, the two researchers collaborated with researchers in library science (mrh) in 2020. Furthermore, mrh collaborated with other library science researchers (nw, fdn, and msb) in 2021.

Cluster 7 is a collaborative network of lecturers in X Institution who conducted research in 2021. Cluster 6 is a collaborative network of lecturers in the taxation sector in 2020. Cluster 10 has the same field as Cluster 6 but with different researchers and years. Even though each cluster is formed due to the same field, this cannot become the main conclusion. In the case of a wider cluster, namely the green cluster, a Departement Z researcher (na) once collaborated with US researchers on good governance of halal products. Then the US researchers collaborated with other researchers on business management through Social Exchange Theory. It confirmed that clusters could be formed from the collaboration of researchers from different fields. One of these researchers will become a cluster with the second researcher if one of them never collaborates again with other researchers in the same field in this research scheme.

The Collaborative Network of *Hibah H*

Figure 8. *Hibah H* 2020-2021

Hibah H consisted of 27 researchers producing 9 titles. Figure 8 shows the researchers forming 9 separate clusters. In addition, 7 collaborative clusters were formed with three researchers,

and 1 cluster was formed with two researchers. Although they were separate, these networks had the same pattern because all researchers in this scheme produced 1 research title. This research scheme only occurred in 2020.

The Collaborative Network of *Hibah I*

Figure 9. Hibah I 2020-2021

Hibah I consisted of 58 researchers producing 20 titles. Figure 9 shows the researchers forming 13 clusters, 2 of which are connected. Cluster 1 consisted of researchers in library science (fdn, apg, nw, and ra), and they had collaborative research in assisting the management of village archives in 2021. In the previous year, 2020, nw worked on community service with researchers in other fields. On the other hand, apg worked with other researchers in 2021. However, the two different collaborations were still related to literacy and information management. This pattern forms Cluster 1 as the widest network. On the other hand, ra had collaborative community service in literacy villages with researchers in library science from Cluster 13 (msb and mrh) in 2020. This collaboration led to a link between Cluster 1 and Cluster 13.

Separate clusters form 3 patterns. First, service collaboration only occurred in 2020 (Cluster 4, 5, 6, 7, and 10). Second, the collaboration only occurred in 2021 (Cluster 8, 9, 11, and 12). Third, repeated collaborations occurred the following year, but one researcher also collaborated with others. This causes the formed cluster to be wider (Cluster 2 and 3).

Based on this description, the collaboration between different researchers resulted in 9 titles over two years. On the other hand, repeated collaborations with different researchers, either in the same year or different years, tend to dominate the Hibah I scheme with 11 titles.

The Collaborative Network of *Hibah DPKM*

Figure 10. *Hibah DPKM* 2020-2021

Hibah DPKM (Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat) consisted of 130 researchers producing 62 titles. Figure 10 shows that the researchers formed 19 clusters, 10 of which were connected. The connected clusters form two clusters. The first cluster is a collaborative network of lecturers in Departemen Y. The clusters consist of Cluster 1, 2, 7, and 9. The second cluster is the collaborative network of lecturers in Departement Z consisting of Cluster 3, 4, 5, 6, and 10.

The researcher in Cluster 1 (su) collaborates with researchers in Cluster 4 (yes), Cluster 5 (akt), and Cluster 6 (ey) on Tourism Destination Promotion in 2020. Then researchers in Cluster 4 (mrz and igep) collaborated with the researchers in cluster 2 (ak) and Cluster 3 (rew) in 2020. Furthermore, the researcher in Cluster 2 (kpk) collaborated with researchers in Cluster 10 (nw and swt) and Cluster 17 (ep) on Tourism Village Development in 2020. The three collaborations resulted in two network clusters: Departement Y and Departement Z. Unfortunately, all of these connections only occurred in 2020.

Furthermore, other researchers in the cluster collaborated with researchers from other clusters in 2020 and 2021. This pattern confirmed that the network of 10 clusters was not directly connected. Several researchers in one cluster acted as liaisons with other different clusters.

These patterns confirmed two interesting findings. First, the same clusters were not necessarily directly connected. This happened in Cluster 1 and 7 (Departemen Y), which were not actually connected to Cluster 2, 9, and 17 (Departemen Y). However, several researchers in Cluster 4 (Departemen Z) collaborated with researchers in these clusters to produce different titles. The connection shows that several researchers within the Departemen Z field acted as liaisons to connect separate clusters on Departemen Y. Second, there were researchers from different clusters within one cluster. One example is ak (Departemen Z), a member of Cluster 2 (Departemen Y). This condition occurred because ak collaborated more with researchers in Departemen Y compared to other Departemen Z researchers in this scheme.

On the other hand, 9 separate clusters form 4 patterns. First, service collaboration only occurred once a year. This pattern occurred in Cluster 12, 13, 16, 18, 19 (in 2021) and Cluster 16 (in 2020). Second, collaboration occurred between the same 4 researchers but on different topics in 2020 and 2021 (Cluster 11, 14, and 15). Cluster 15 had a special characteristic because the researchers only included *assistant professor* and *associate professor*. Third, collaboration occurred between the same researchers, but several researchers collaborated with other researchers in 2020 and 2021. This pattern occurred in Cluster 9, which consisted of more researchers than in other separate clusters. The researchers performed repeated service with bip, atw, and bap for two years. On the other hand, the researchers were also doing service with sj and h in 2020 and asm and ty in 2021. Furthermore, the researchers did not collaborate with others in the *Hibah DPKM* scheme. This condition caused the clusters to separate from each other.

The 2020 Collaborative Network

Figure 11. The 2020 Collaborative Network

X INSTITUTION's research and community service took place with 137 researchers producing 97 titles in 2020. Figure 11 shows the researchers forming 11 clusters, 9 of which are connected. Cluster 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 refers to the group of researchers in the field of Departemen Y. The widest network (Cluster 1) is the network of these researchers in 2020. On the other hand, Cluster 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, and 11 refer to the group of researchers in the field of Departement Z.

There are 2 separate clusters (Cluster 11 and 13) in 2020. Cluster 11 is a network of *assistant professor* and *associate professor* collaborating through *Hibah B*, *Hibah DPKM*, and *Hibah C* schemes. On the other hand, Cluster 13 is for researchers who collaborated only through the scheme of *Hibah G*.

The 2021 Collaborative Network

Figure 12. The 2021 Collaborative Network

Figure 12 shows the collaborative network and X INSTITUTION's community service from 132 researchers who produced 91 titles in 2021. Compared to 2020, the number of researchers decreased by 5 people, and more clusters were formed (15 clusters), but connected clusters increased (14 clusters). Cluster 1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 12, 14, and 15 are a network of researchers within the field of Departemen Y. On the other hand, Cluster 2, 5, 9, 10, 11, and 13 are a network of researchers within the field of Departemen Z. There is only one separate cluster (Cluster 15) in 2021. The researchers in those clusters only collaborated through the *Hibah A* and Hibah DPKM.

The Collaborative Network of Research

Figure 13. The Collaborative Network of Research Types

The collaborative research consisted of 122 researchers from 2020 to 2021. Figure 12 shows the researchers forming 18 clusters, 14 of which are connected. The researchers produced 106 titles through 5 schemes. The scheme consists of *Doktor Associate professor*, *Doktor Non-Associate professor*, *Hibah C*, *Hibah D*, *Hibah E*, *Hibah F* and *Hibah G*. Each researcher produced 1 to 7 titles. The researchers coded sw, ec, and msd produced the highest number of documents with 7 titles. On the other hand, the researcher's links (the number indicating how many researchers a researcher has collaborated with) that were more than or equal to 10 are for sw, reu, and apg. These findings confirmed that researchers producing many documents did not necessarily produce many links that described how often one researcher collaborated with other researchers.

Researchers producing 2 documents acted as liaisons between clusters (gen, rhs, dnfr, sj, taf, and mrp). This is the reason why collaborative research tends to form interconnected networks. Further identification revealed that the 14 connected clusters formed 2 clusters. The left cluster (Cluster 2, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 15) formed a separate pattern from the right cluster (Cluster 1, 3, 4, 6, 13, and 18). However, the two clusters are related. The researcher in Cluster 5 (sj) collaborated with mkm. Mkm had collaborated with researchers in Cluster 5 (apy and arh). On the other hand, sj conducted research with researchers in Cluster 1 (reu) and Cluster 4 (bs and mn). The research took place through an international cooperation scheme discussing University Forest Policy in 2020.

There are 4 separate clusters (Cluster 12, 14, 17, and 16). The research in those clusters occurred through the scheme of *Hibah H* (Cluster 14), *Hibah B* (Cluster 17), and *Hibah C* (Cluster 16). Cluster 12 was formed when the researcher (sh, a professor) collaborated with *associate professor* through the scheme of *Hibah D*. On the other hand, ah also collaborate through the *Hibah E* scheme with different researchers. The separate network occurred because researchers in the 4 clusters did not conduct research with other clusters of researchers in 2020.

The Collaborative Network of Community Services

Figure 14. The Collaborative Network of Community Services

X Institution's collaborative network of community service consisted of 138 researchers from 2020 to 2021. Figure 14, the researchers formed 18 clusters, 13 of which were connected. The researchers produced 82 titles through 2 schemes. The schemes were *Hibah I* and *Hibah DPKM*. Each author produced 1 to 4 titles. Researchers nw, mrh, ep, kpk, rrh, df, aw, s, ad lhu produced the highest number of documents, 4 titles. In this regard, researchers with more than 7 links were nw, mrh, mrz, ep, kpk, rrh, su, and lh. These findings confirmed that the number of documents produced tends to be balanced with the number of links that described how often one researcher collaborated with other researchers. In addition, the researchers produced more than two titles served as liaisons between clusters. This forms a connected, collaborative network of community service.

On the other hand, there were 5 separate clusters (Cluster 7, 14, 16, and 18). The separate clusters formed three characteristics. First, community service was collaborative with the same authors and continuous topics from 2020 to 2021 (Cluster 14). Second, community service was

done with the same authors but on different topics from 2020 to 2021 (Cluster 16, 15, 18). Third, community service occurred in the same year and scheme (2020-Hibah DPKM) but with different authors and topics (Cluster 7).

The Cumulative Collaborative Network of 2020-2021

Figure 15. Cumulative Network 2020-2021

The collaborative research and community service cumulatively comprised 154 researchers from 2020 to 2021. Figure 15 shows the researchers forming 14 interconnected clusters and 188 titles. The interesting thing is that based on the 2020 and 2021 collaborative research and community service, they form separate clusters. However, the entire cluster was connected in a cumulative collaborative network. This condition occurred due to several collaborations as follows.

First, the researcher in Cluster 13 (dnfr) in 2020 collaborated again with other clusters of researchers through the *Hibah DPKM* scheme in 2021. Second, the researcher in cluster 11 (fdn) collaborated with more researchers from other clusters through the *Hibah I* scheme, *Hibah E*, and *Hibah F* in 2021. Third, based on the 2021 network, the researchers in Cluster 15 were separated. However, the previous year, sr collaborated with fellow researchers through the *Hibah A*, *Hibah DPKM*, and *Hibah F*. On the other hand, act also collaborated with other researchers through the *Hibah DPKM* scheme in 2020. These findings confirmed that

researchers could be connected to different schemes, types, and years.

Cluster 1 and 2 have similarities because they were collaborations between lecturers in Departement Z. However, the difference was that half of the Cluster 1 researchers had a high number of titles and links compared to other clusters. The researchers in Cluster 1 all had produced a title in 2020 and were involved in research. Some of these researchers worked across 9 research and service schemes. Researchers in Cluster 2 were mostly *assistant professor* and *associate professor*. However, these researchers were never involved in *Hibah I*, *Hibah E*, and *Hibah G*.

Cluster 3, 4, and 5 have something in common: collaboration between lecturers in Departement Y and community service involvement. However, the difference is that half of the researchers in Cluster 3 had many titles and links and were not involved in the *Hibah B* scheme. Meanwhile, all researchers in Cluster 4 produced documents in 2021 but were not involved in the *Hibah E* scheme. Meanwhile, the researchers in Cluster 5 worked across 9 schemes.

Cluster 6 is a network of lecturers of library science. All researchers produced documents in 2021 but had never been involved in *Hibah C* and *Hibah G*.

Cluster 7 is a collaboration of lecturers in Departement Y who had never been involved in the scheme of *Hibah B* and *Hibah G*. Cluster 8 is a mixed collaboration network (Departement Y and Departement Z). Almost all researchers were *assistant professor* and *associate professor*. All researchers were never involved in *Hibah B*, *Hibah C*, and *Hibah G*.

Cluster 9 and 10 are collaborations between lecturers of Departement Y and taxation. The difference is that all researchers in cluster 9 produced a title in 2021. These researchers were never involved in *Hibah A* and *Hibah D*. All researchers of Cluster 10 produced 2020 titles; some researchers worked across 9 schemes.

Cluster 11 and 12 are collaborations of Departement Z lecturers and were never involved in *Hibah A* and *Hibah D*. The difference is that all researchers in Cluster 11 produced documents in 2021. On the other hand, cluster 12 produced documents in 2020 and 2021, but they were also not involved in the scheme of *Hibah G*. This condition was strengthened by the fact that the researchers in that cluster only consisted of *assistant professor*, *associate professor*, and *full professor*.

Researchers in Cluster 13 and 14 were not involved in *Hibah B*, *Hibah C*, and *Hibah E*. The difference is that Cluster 13 is a collaborative network of lecturers in taxation. On the other hand, Cluster 14 is a collaborative network of *assistant professor* and *associate professor* in Departement Y and tourism that produced documents for 2020 and 2021.

These clusters formed two clusters of collaborative networks. The left cluster is a collaborative network of lecturers in Departement Y (Cluster 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 13, and 14). On the other hand, the right cluster is a collaborative network of lecturers in Departement Z (Cluster 1, 2, 6, 8, 11, and 12). Based on the network map, the relationship between the two clusters occurred through researchers sj-mkm, ep, lhu, aqm, ya, ala and akt. In addition, the researchers acted as liaisons through *Hibah I* and *Hibah DPKM* in 2020 or 2021. In addition to connection through research,

the connection also occurred through community services. The schemes are *Hibah E 2020* and *Hibah F 2021*.

Based on the characteristics, the cumulative collaborative network formed separate clusters due to different fields of knowledge and the involvement of research schemes. However, clusters were interrelated when several researchers collaborated through a certain scheme or year.

Distribution of Schemes in Departement Y and Departement Z

The collaborative network map tended to form two clusters, namely the Departement Y network and the Departement Z network. Each was formed when the authors conducted research or community service through a certain scheme. Based on these findings, the scheme influenced the formation of a cumulative collaborative network pattern. Thus, we further identified the distribution of the scheme based on the collaborative network.

Figure 16. Cumulative Distribution of Titles per Scheme in Department Y and Department Z 2020-2021

Figure 16 shows the collaborative network of lecturers in the Department Y dominated *Hibah I*, *Hibah F*, *Hibah G*, *Hibah D*, *Hibah G*, and *Hibah DPKM*. However, the network only had a difference of 1 title with the Department Z lecturer network in *Hibah DPKM*. Meanwhile, the collaborative network of Department Z lecturers produced more titles, but with a difference of only 1-2 titles in *Hibah C* and *Hibah A*. On the other hand, the two network clusters produced

the same number of titles through *Hibah B* and *Hibah E*. Cumulatively, the connection between the Department Z and Department Y networks occurred through 4 schemes, consisting of *Hibah DPKM*, *Hibah I*, *Hibah F*, *Hibah G*, and *Hibah B*.

CONCLUSION

The collaboration network of 9 research and community service schemes of X INSTITUTION tends to be stable in frequency from 2020 to 2021. These schemes form special patterns. *Hibah A*, *Hibah C*, and *Hibah Ht* end to form separate collaborative networks due to collaboration with the same or different researchers for two years. On the other hand, *Hibah B*, *Hibah D*, *Hibah E*, *Hibah F*, *Hibah I*, and *Hibah DPKM* have several authors acting as the center of collaboration so that the network has several connected clusters. Even though each cluster is formed due to the same field, this cannot become the main conclusion. In a broader case, clusters can be formed from the collaboration of researchers from different fields.

As happened in *Hibah DPKM*, several researchers in Department Z act as liaisons for separate collaborative clusters of Departemen Y. There is a separate collaboration if the network is based on the research ad community service in 2021 and 2021. Clusters form special characteristics due to differences in fields of science, frequency, links of each researcher, and research schemes. But cumulatively, the network is connected to form two clusters: Departement Z and Departemen Y. *Hibah DPKM*, *Hibah I*, *Hibah F*, *Hibah G*, and *Hibah B* are the connectors of those clusters.

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